

Healing outcomes after placental membrane-based skin substitute allografts in multiple wound types in routine care: a retrospective case series from a product registry

Julie Schottenstein¹, Mohanad Eltahir², Mario Cala³, Juliette Perez⁴, Brian Gillette⁵, & Paul Fawson⁶

¹The Schottenstein Center, ²Pima Foot and Ankle Surgery, ^{3,4}PerfectFeetCare Podiatry Centers, ⁵Droice Research, & ⁶Acesso Biologics

Abstract

Background: Chronic wounds are common, debilitating, and expensive. Even with evidence-based standard care (e.g., offloading, compression, pressure redistribution, debridement, infection control, etc.), many wounds fail to heal on expected timelines. Placental membrane-based skin substitutes are used as adjuncts once standard care is optimized. However, real-world outcomes in routine, multi-etiology practice remain less well characterized.

Objective: To describe healing outcomes in routine clinical practice among adults with diverse chronic wound types treated with placental membrane-based allografts.

Methods: Retrospective observational case series using a previously established product registry of routine wound-care encounters. Adults with ≥ 1 product-based allograft application and ≥ 1 post-index visit were eligible; one index wound per patient was analyzed, with secondary summaries for all product-treated wounds. **Primary endpoint:** Complete wound closure at 12-week (100% epithelialization, no drainage or dressing required). **Secondary endpoints:** Time to closure (among healed wounds), $\geq 50\%$ area reduction at 4 weeks, and partial area reduction (PAR) at 12-weeks among non-healed wounds.

Results: Fifty-one patients (67 wounds) were included; most index wounds were diabetic foot ulcers (74.5%). Multimorbidity was common (e.g., diabetes with neuropathy, peripheral

arterial/venous disease, chronic kidney disease), and wounds were often longstanding (median duration 91 days). In a complete case subset with evaluable 12-week status intended to reflect real-world effectiveness in routine clinical practice in which patients cease followup after their wound is healed (N=15), closure was 13/15 (86.7%; 95% CI, 65.3%-98.6%). In a conservative calculation of 12-week closure, the wound healing rate was 16.0% (8/50) in index wounds and 19.7% (13/66) in all wounds. Care patterns reflected weekly use (median ~5-6 visits and ~5 applications over 12 weeks). Many non-healed wounds showed partial area reduction at 12 weeks.

Conclusions: In routine care across diverse etiologies and substantial comorbidity, placental membrane-based allografts were associated with variable 12-week closure proportions, early improvement in ~50% of wounds, and rapid closure among responders, with wide heterogeneity in trajectories. These benchmarks highlight the need for understanding efficacy in complex, real-world patient populations, and may inform clinical planning and support future comparative studies.

Keywords: chronic wounds; diabetic foot ulcer; venous leg ulcer; pressure ulcer; amniotic membrane; skin substitute; registry.

Introduction

Chronic wounds, including diabetic foot ulcers (DFUs), venous leg ulcers (VLUs), and pressure ulcers (PU), impose a substantial clinical and economic burden, with high risks of infection, hospitalization, limb loss, and impaired quality of life¹. Despite optimized etiology-specific care (e.g., controlling comorbid conditions; offloading for DFUs; compression for VLUs; pressure redistribution) and standard wound management (regular debridement as indicated, infection control, moisture balance, and vascular assessment/intervention), healing is often protracted and recurrences common¹⁻¹⁰.

When wound healing fails to progress adequately under standard management, biologic skin substitutes, such as human placental membranes, may facilitate improved healing outcomes.

Placental membrane allografts provide extracellular matrix architecture and bioactive cues that facilitate vascularization and reepithelialization and modulate inflammation¹¹⁻¹⁴. Across controlled studies, several placental membranes have improved healing outcomes versus standard care in selected populations: randomized trials in DFU and VLU have reported higher 12-week closure and/or faster healing with placental membranes (e.g., viable cryopreserved or dehydrated amnion/chorion) compared with standard care alone¹⁵⁻¹⁸. These findings have been supported by confirmatory trials and meta-analyses, while acknowledging heterogeneity across products, indications, and study designs^{19,20}. Real-world analyses in Medicare cohorts further associate placenta-derived allografts with lower recurrence and mortality and fewer adverse outcomes than standard care, suggesting potential benefits at scale²¹⁻²³.

Despite this evidence base, multi-etiology descriptions of wound healing outcomes under treatment with placental membrane-based allografts in routine care settings with real-world study cohorts remain limited. Such case series can provide pragmatic benchmarks (e.g., proportions achieving complete closure at clinically relevant time horizons and improvement trajectories)

that complement controlled trials and inform future research and decision-making across diverse wound types, especially in more complex, real-world populations that include more severe disease and comorbidities that are typically excluded from clinical trials. Furthermore, transparent real-world outcomes help inform clinical decision-making and policy regarding appropriate use and access²⁴.

The present retrospective case series describes routine care outcomes for adults with multiple wound types treated with placental membrane-based skin substitutes in a previously established product registry; the primary endpoint was 12-week complete closure, with secondary endpoints of time to closure (among healed wounds), $\geq 50\%$ area reduction at 4 weeks following treatment initiation with placental membranes, and 12-week partial area reduction.

Materials and Methods

Design, setting, and participants

A retrospective, observational case series was conducted using a previously established product registry of routine wound-care encounters from outpatient and hospital-based programs. Adults (≥ 18 years) with at least one documented application of a study placental membrane-based skin substitute and ≥ 1 post-index visit were eligible for analysis. For any patients with multiple wounds, one index wound was selected for summary analyses based on the largest wound at baseline or if tied the longest duration. The data period was from February 2025 through the database lock used for this analysis (final data freeze: October 14, 2025). Institutional Review Board oversight was obtained with an Exempt Category 4 determination for secondary research on existing data.

Data source

Data were extracted from the “Clinical registry collecting real-world evidence on wound care treatments” (ClinicalTrials.gov NCT06328010; ISRCTN 96261955), a U.S. multicenter

observational cohort capturing routine wound-care encounters in outpatient and post-acute settings. Adults with ulcers or chronic wounds receiving standard care and/or advanced grafts were enrolled under minimal clinical exclusions; therapy was determined by treating clinicians, and outcomes were recorded during usual care.

Exposure, outcomes, and assessments

Exposure was clinician-directed application of specific placental membrane-based skin substitutes (placental membrane triple layer A (PMTL-A); placental membrane double layer (PMDL); placental membrane triple layer B (PMTL-B)^{*}) as part of routine care. The index visit was defined as the visit with the first exposure. The primary endpoint was complete wound closure by 12 weeks, defined as 100% epithelialization with no drainage/dressings (as indicated by a 'closed' assessment in the registry). The secondary endpoints were: (1) time-to-closure (days from index to confirmed closure among healed wounds), (2) early improvement at 4 weeks ($\geq 50\%$ area reduction from index), (3) PAR at 12 weeks among wounds remaining open.

Baseline variables included demographics; wound etiology (DFU/VLU/PU/other), location, area, and duration.

Statistical analysis

Analyses were descriptive. Proportions were summarized with exact (Clopper-Pearson) 95% confidence intervals; continuous variables with mean \pm SD and median [IQR]. The primary analysis used an intent-to-treat style (primary-evaluable) set defined as all index wounds with ≥ 1 post-index visit.

^{*} Acceso TL = placental membrane triple layer A; Neostim DL = placental membrane double layer; Neostim TL = placental membrane triple layer B

In real-world clinical settings, subjects frequently A) are lost to follow up and B) cease follow up after wound closure. To account for this, for the 12-week complete-closure endpoint in this set, two methods were used. The first was last observation carried forward (LOCF), which was applied to patients without a 12-week visit: the last recorded wound status was carried forward to week 12 (wounds counted as closed if a closure event had been recorded prior to loss to follow-up; otherwise counted as open), which provides a conservative estimate of wound closure status (i.e., is likely an underestimate of closure rate because it assumes no patient wounds lost to followup would have closed). A complete case analysis was also summarized for wounds with an ascertainable 12-week status (closed by 12 weeks or documented open at 12 weeks without LOCF), which may better reflect real-world effectiveness of products because patients frequently cease followup after their wound is healed.

Time to closure was reported among wounds that healed, measured as days from index to the first recorded closure; wounds without closure were not included, and no survival modeling was performed. Early improvement at 4 weeks ($\geq 50\%$ area reduction) and 12-week partial area reduction (PAR) were summarized using LOCF. Product- and wound-type summaries were descriptive. No other imputation was performed. Analyses were conducted using R (version 4.5.1).

Results

Cohort and baseline characteristics

Fifty-one patients were included with 67 product-treated wounds overall; 21.6% (11/51) had multiple treated wounds (median 2, range 2-5) (Table 1). Among index wounds, etiologies were DFU 74.5% (38/51), VLU 7.8% (4/51), PU 7.8% (4/51), and other 9.8% (5/51); across all wounds, etiologies were DFU 76.1%, VLU 6.0%, PU 7.5%, other 10.4%. Baseline area (median

[IQR]) was 4.2 cm² [2.0-16.1] for index wounds and 3.8 cm² [1.4-12.0] for all wounds; baseline duration was 91 days for both (index [52–320]; all wounds [46-274]).

The patient population showed a high burden of conditions associated with impaired healing, including type 2 diabetes (with neuropathy or Charcot changes in many cases), peripheral arterial/venous disease or chronic venous hypertension, chronic kidney disease/end-stage renal disease, congestive heart failure/atrial fibrillation, prior amputation, lymphedema, and DVT (Supplementary Table 1). Several patients had multiple cardiometabolic and vascular comorbidities concurrently (e.g., diabetes with CKD and PVD), suggesting a cohort that would often be excluded from typical randomized trials. The wound-level listing further illustrates case-mix severity: durations up to 4 years and very large baseline areas (e.g., 80-83 cm²) occurred in a subset, while others were small and early-stage (Supplementary Table 2).

Treatment utilization

Index wounds had a mean (SD) 5.5 (2.8) clinic visits (median [IQR] 5 [3-8]) and 5.0 (2.8) allograft applications (median [IQR] 5 [3-7]); among wounds with ≥ 2 applications, the median [IQR] application interval was 7 [7-7] days. Across all wounds, visits averaged 5.7 (2.6) (median [IQR] 6 [3-8]), applications 5.1 (2.7) (median [IQR] 5 [3-7]), and the median [IQR] interval 7 days [7-8]. These patterns reflected weekly use in routine practice. Out of all wounds, 28 were treated with both PMDL and PMTL-B over their course, 25 were treated with PMTL-B only, 7 with PMTL-A only, and 6 with PMDL only.

Primary healing endpoint

Among index wounds (primary-evaluable N=50), 8/50 (16.0%; 95% CI, 7.2%-29.1%) achieved complete closure by 12 weeks (Table 2). Across all wounds (primary-evaluable N=66), 12-week closure was 13/66 (19.7%; 95% CI, 10.9%-31.3%). In a complete case subset with evaluable 12-week status (N=15), closure was 13/15 (86.7%; 95% CI, 65.3%-98.6%).

Secondary healing endpoints

Time to closure (among healed) was 24 days (IQR 7-55) for index wounds and 21 days (IQR 7-49) for all wounds (Table 2). Early improvement at 4 weeks occurred in 23/50 (46.0%; 95% CI, 31.8%-60.7%) among index wounds and 34/66 (51.5%; 95% CI, 38.9%–64.0%) across all wounds with evaluable measurements. Twelve-week PAR among wounds open at 12 weeks averaged 37.4% (SD 65.5%) with median 48.9% [18.4%-81.2%] for index wounds, and 37.7% (SD 63.7%) with median 50.8% [18.8%-78.7%] for all wounds.

Outcomes by product

Across all wounds, 12-week closure proportions (n/N, % [95% CI]) were: PMTL-A only: 1/7, 14.3% [0.4%-57.9%]; PMDL only: 2/6, 33.3% [4.3%-77.7%]; PMTL-B only: 4/25, 16.0% [4.5%-36.1%]; PMDL/PMTL-B combined: 6/28, 21.4% [8.3%-41.0%] (Table 3). Median time-to-closure among healed ranged 7-54 days across products. Early improvement at 4 weeks was 3/7 (42.9% [9.9%-81.6%]) for PMTL-A only, 4/6 (66.7% [22.3%-95.7%]) for PMDL only, 13/25 (52.0% [31.3%-72.2%]) for PMTL-B only, and 14/28 (50.0% [30.6%-69.4%]) for PMDL/PMTL-B combined. Among wounds still open at 12 weeks, PAR (mean±SD; median [IQR]) was: PMTL-A only: -35.6% ± 177.4%; 39.4% [-52.5%-56.3%]; PMDL only: 54.9% ± 29.6%; 55.4% [41.4%-69.0%]; PMTL-B only: 48.1% ± 34.7%; 52.9% [22.2%-73.0%]; PMDL/PMTL-B combined: 29.1% ± 65.0%; 50.8% [3.9%-77.5%]. These product-level findings should be interpreted cautiously given very small strata and likely selection differences by wound severity and chronicity.

Patient wound cases

Wound-area trajectories for index and all wounds are shown in Figure 1. The patient medical history listing (Supplementary Table 1) summarizes comorbidities at registry enrollment, and the patient wound-level listing (Supplementary Table 2) documents per-wound baseline

area/duration, number of visits/applications, products used, percent change, and time-to-closure when applicable.

Discussion

This multi-etiology case series offers pragmatic outcome benchmarks for placental membrane-based allografts in routine practice. In a complete case analysis intended to account for patients lost to followup in real-world practice, 86.7% of wounds achieved complete closure; with a conservative analysis using LOCF, by 12 weeks, 16.0% of index wounds and 19.7% of all treated wounds achieved complete closure. Among wounds that healed, median time-to-closure ~3-4 weeks. Early improvement ($\geq 50\%$ area reduction) was observed in 77.8% in complete cases and ~46-52% of evaluable wounds at 4 weeks, and distributions of 12-week PAR among wounds that remained open indicated substantial partial contraction in many cases, albeit with wide variability.

The real-world registry population exhibited a comorbidity burden and wound characteristics that are frequently excluded from controlled trials: multiple cardiometabolic and vascular diseases (e.g., diabetes with neuropathy or Charcot, peripheral arterial/venous disease, CKD/ESRD, CHF/AF), prior amputations, and prolonged wound duration (up to 4 years) were common features (Table 4, Supplementary Tables 1-2). Additionally, no patients were excluded for smoking status or poor clinic follow up. Such factors are well-known predictors of delayed healing and complications; they likely contributed to lower 12-week closure proportions compared with many RCTs of placental allografts that enroll narrower DFU/VLU populations under standardized co-interventions and follow-up. Patients with CKD fared particularly poorly, with the four case patients (five wounds) having an average 86.8% worsening of their skin ulcers (percent increases wound size = 0%, 56.3%, 100%, -22.2%, 300%, respectively). At the same

time, median time-to-closure among those who healed was short, and several wounds achieved rapid closure (≤ 1 -2 weeks), illustrating the heterogeneity of real-world response.

These findings also reflect the heterogeneity of real-world wound application and treatment regimens, which were highly varied in the dataset. Treatment courses ranged from 4 weeks to 3 years, with an average clinic visit ranging from 0.083 visits/month (1 visit in 2 years) to 9.0 visits/month (9 visits in 4 weeks) (average = 2.24 visits/month). Skin graft applications ranged from one to nine total grafts over the course of individual wound treatment. These findings highlight the opportunity for more controlled efficacy studies in complex, real-world populations that are found in routine clinical practice.

Limitations

Limitations of this study include a single-arm design; modest sample size with sparse subgroups; reliance on routine care settings and documentation; incomplete capture of 4- and 12-week windows; and use of last observation carried forward (LOCF) for 12-week closure in the primary-evaluable analysis, which can bias estimates if loss to follow-up is informative.

Apparent differences by product (e.g., higher 12-week closure with PMTL-A only; very short time-to-closure among healed with PMDL only) should be viewed as hypothesis-generating: strata were small and likely reflect clinical selection (e.g., product chosen for smaller, more acute wounds vs chronic, larger lesions), not comparative effectiveness. These factors warrant cautious interpretation and motivate prospective, comparative research with adequate power, bias control, and adjudicated endpoints.

Conclusions

In a real-world, multi-etiology cohort, including many patients with substantial comorbidity burdens and longstanding wounds, placental membrane-based allografts were associated with 12-week closure in 86.7% of complete case wounds, 16.0% of index wounds, and 19.7% of all

treated wounds, median time-to-closure ~3-4 weeks among healed wounds, and ~46-78% early improvement ($\geq 50\%$ reduction 4 weeks post initial application). These findings supply pragmatic benchmarks and support the design of larger, comparative studies that account for comorbidity and chronicity in high-risk, routine-care populations that are often ineligible for RCTs.

References

1. Sen CK. Human Wound and Its Burden: Updated 2022 Compendium of Estimates. *Adv Wound Care (New Rochelle)*. 2023;12(12):657. doi:10.1089/WOUND.2023.0150
2. Bus SA, Armstrong DG, Crews RT, et al. Guidelines on offloading foot ulcers in persons with diabetes (IWGDF 2023 update). *Diabetes Metab Res Rev*. 2024;40(3):e3647. doi:10.1002/DMRR.3647
3. Chen P, Vilorio NC, Dhatariya K, et al. Guidelines on interventions to enhance healing of foot ulcers in people with diabetes (IWGDF 2023 update). *Diabetes Metab Res Rev*. 2024;40(3). doi:10.1002/DMRR.3644,
4. Marston W, Tang J, Kirsner RS, Ennis W. Wound healing society 2015 update on guidelines for venous ulcers. *Wound Repair and Regeneration*. 2016;24(1):136-144. doi:10.1111/WRR.12394,
5. NPIAP — Prevention and Treatment of Pressure Ulcers/Injuries: Clinical Practice Guideline. Accessed July 16, 2025. <https://internationalguideline.com/the-international-guideline>
6. Prevention and Treatment of Pressure Ulcers/Injuries: Clinical Practice Guideline. Accessed October 19, 2025. <https://internationalguideline.com/the-international-guideline>
7. Pressure Ulcer Guideline | EPUAP org. Accessed October 19, 2025. <https://epuap.org/pu-guidelines/>
8. O'Donnell TF, Passman MA, Marston WA, et al. Management of venous leg ulcers: Clinical practice guidelines of the Society for Vascular Surgery® and the American Venous Forum. *J Vasc Surg*. 2014;60(2):3S-59S. doi:10.1016/j.jvs.2014.04.049
9. Hingorani A, Lamuraglia GM, Henke P, et al. The management of diabetic foot: A clinical practice guideline by the Society for Vascular Surgery in collaboration with the American Podiatric Medical Association and the Society for Vascular Medicine. *J Vasc Surg*. 2016;63(2):3S-21S. doi:10.1016/j.jvs.2015.10.003
10. Lavery LA, Davis KE, Berriman SJ, et al. WHS guidelines update: Diabetic foot ulcer treatment guidelines. *Wound Repair and Regeneration*. 2016;24(1):112-126. doi:10.1111/WRR.12391,

11. Koob TJ, Rennert R, Zabek N, et al. Biological properties of dehydrated human amnion/chorion composite graft: implications for chronic wound healing. *Int Wound J.* 2013;10(5):493-500. doi:10.1111/IWJ.12140
12. Koob TJ, Lim JJ, Masee M, et al. Angiogenic properties of dehydrated human amnion/chorion allografts: therapeutic potential for soft tissue repair and regeneration. *Vasc Cell.* 2014;6(1):10. doi:10.1186/2045-824X-6-10
13. Heydari P, Mojahedi M, Javaherchi P, Sharifi M, Kharazi AZ. Advances and impact of human amniotic membrane and human amniotic-based materials in wound healing application. *Int J Biol Macromol.* 2024;281:136596. doi:10.1016/J.IJBIOMAC.2024.136596
14. Parmar UPS, Surico PL, Scarabosio A, et al. Amniotic Membrane Transplantation for Wound Healing, Tissue Regeneration and Immune Modulation. *Stem Cell Reviews and Reports 2025.* Published online May 14, 2025:1-21. doi:10.1007/S12015-025-10892-X
15. Lavery LA, Fulmer J, Shebetka KA, et al. The efficacy and safety of Grafix® for the treatment of chronic diabetic foot ulcers: Results of a multi-centre, controlled, randomised, blinded, clinical trial. *Int Wound J.* 2014;11(5):554-560. doi:10.1111/IWJ.12329,
16. Tettelbach W, Cazzell S, Reyzelman AM, Sigal F, Caporusso JM, Agnew PS. A confirmatory study on the efficacy of dehydrated human amnion/chorion membrane dHACM allograft in the management of diabetic foot ulcers: A prospective, multicentre, randomised, controlled study of 110 patients from 14 wound clinics. *Int Wound J.* 2019;16(1):19-29. doi:10.1111/IWJ.12976,
17. Serena TE, Orgill DP, Armstrong DG, et al. A Multicenter, Randomized, Controlled, Clinical Trial Evaluating Dehydrated Human Amniotic Membrane in the Treatment of Venous Leg Ulcers. *Plast Reconstr Surg.* 2022;150(5):1128. doi:10.1097/PRS.00000000000009650
18. Serena TE, Carter MJ, Le LT, et al. A multicenter, randomized, controlled clinical trial evaluating the use of dehydrated human amnion/chorion membrane allografts and multilayer compression therapy vs.

- multilayer compression therapy alone in the treatment of venous leg ulcers. *Wound Repair and Regeneration*. 2014;22(6):688-693. doi:10.1111/WRR.12227,
19. Mohammed YA, Farouk HK, Gbreel MI, et al. Human amniotic membrane products for patients with diabetic foot ulcers. do they help? a systematic review and meta-analysis. *J Foot Ankle Res*. 2022;15(1):71. doi:10.1186/S13047-022-00575-Y
 20. Alomairi AA, Alhatlani RA, Alharbi SM, et al. Assessing the Application and Effectiveness of Human Amniotic Membrane in the Management of Venous and Diabetic Ulcers: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis of Randomized Controlled Trials. *Cureus*. 2024;16(3):e56659. doi:10.7759/CUREUS.56659
 21. Padula W V., Ramanathan S, Cohen BG, Chingcuanco F, Steel P, Herzer KR. Comparative Effectiveness of Amniotic and Chorionic Grafts in the Treatment of Lower-Extremity Diabetic Ulcers Using U.S. Medicare Real-World Evidence (2018–2022): A Retrospective Observational Cohort. *Adv Wound Care (New Rochelle)*. Published online January 22, 2025. doi:10.1089/WOUND.2024.0141/SUPPL_FILE/WOUND.2024.0141_SUPPL_APPENDIX_SA1.PDF,
 22. Carter MJ, DaVanzo J, Haught R, Nusgart M, Cartwright D, Fife CE. Chronic wound prevalence and the associated cost of treatment in Medicare beneficiaries: changes between 2014 and 2019. *J Med Econ*. 2023;26(1):894-901. doi:10.1080/13696998.2023.2232256
 23. Davanzo J, Hartzman A, Surfield C, Dobson A. Cryopreserved Placental Membrane Allograft Reduces the Likelihood of Developing a New or Recurring Foot Ulcer and All-Cause Mortality in Diabetic Patients When Compared with Other Cellular- and Tissue-Based Products. *Adv Wound Care (New Rochelle)*. 2023;12(4):169. doi:10.1089/WOUND.2021.0123
 24. Tettelbach W, Armstrong DG, Driver V, et al. Safeguarding access, fiscal responsibility and innovation: a comprehensive reimbursement framework for CAMPs to preserve the Medicare Trust Fund. <https://doi.org/1012968/jowc20250396>. Published online September 3, 2025:1-10. doi:10.12968/JOWC.2025.0396

Figures

Figure 1. Healing trajectories for all wounds.

Healing trajectories for all wounds. The left panel shows the wound area reduction over time for wounds with a baseline area of <20cm², while the right panel shows the healing trajectory for wounds with a baseline of ≥20cm².

Figure 2. Wound closure by 12 weeks

Tables

Table 1. Baseline characteristics.

Patients (N)	51
Age (years), mean (SD)	63.7 (12.9)
Female, n/N (%)	17/50 (33.3%)
Total product-treated wounds (N)	67
Patients with multiple treated wounds, n/N (%)	11/51 (21.6%)
Wounds per multi-wound patient, median (range)	2 (2-5)
Wound etiology (index only), n (%)	DFU: 38 (74.5%) VLU: 4 (7.8%) PU: 4 (7.8%) Other: 5 (9.8%)
Wound etiology (all wounds), n (%)	DFU: 51 (76.1%) VLU: 4 (6.0%) PU: 5 (7.5%) Other: 7 (10.4%)
Baseline area (index), median [IQR] (cm ²)	4.2 [2.0-16.1]
Baseline area (all wounds), median [IQR] (cm ²)	3.8 [1.4-12.0]
Baseline duration (index), median [IQR] (days)	91 [52-320]
Baseline duration (all wounds), median [IQR] (days)	91 [46-274]

Table 2. Outcomes: 12-week closure, $\geq 50\%$ reduction at 4 weeks, and 12-week PAR.

Population	N	Closed by 12w N (%) [95% CI]	Days to closure median [IQR]	Early improvement at 4w n (%) [95% CI]	12w PAR (%) among open (mean \pm SD; median [IQR])
Index wounds, primary- evaluable	50	8 (16.0%) [7.2%- 29.1%]	24 [7-55]	23 (46.0%) [31.8%– 60.7%]	37.4 \pm 65.5; 48.9 [18.4-81.2]
All wounds, primary- evaluable	66	13 (19.7%) [10.9%-31.3%]	21 [7-49]	34 (51.5%) [38.9%– 64.0%]	37.7 \pm 63.7; 50.8 [18.8-78.7]
All wounds, complete cases	15	13 (86.7%) [65.3%–98.6%]	21 [7–49]	14 (77.8%) [52.4%– 93.6%]	NA

Primary-evaluable: ≥ 2 visits; 12-week closure intent-to treat; last observation carried forward for patients lost to follow up.

Complete cases: subset with evaluable 12-week status (closed by or open at 12 weeks).

Table 3. Outcomes by products used for all wounds.

Product	N	Closed by 12w N (%) [95% CI]	Time to closure for healed, median days [IQR]	Early improvement at 4w n (%) [95% CI]	12w PAR among open (mean±SD; median [IQR])
PMTL-A only	7	1 (14.3%) [0.4-57.9]	15	3 (42.9%) [9.9-81.6]	-35.6±177.4; 39.4 [-52.5-56.3]
PMDL only	6	2 (33.3%) [4.3-77.7]	7 [7-7]	4 (66.7%) [22.3-95.7]	54.9±29.6; 55.4 [41.4-69.0]
PMTL-B only	25	4 (16.0%) [4.5-36.1]	10 [7-26]	13 (52%) [31.3-72.2]	48.1±34.7; 52.9 [22.2-73.0]
PMDL/PMTL-B	28	6 (21.4%) [8.3-41.0]	42 [30-54]	14 (50%) [30.6-69.4]	29.1±65.0; 50.8 [3.9-77.5]

Table 4. Comorbidity burden in study population.

Covariate	N	%
Diabetes mellitus	48	64.9%
Cardiovascular disease	44	59.5%
Peripheral neuropathy	18	24.3%
Peripheral arterial disease	13	17.6%
Major depression	9	12.2%
Chronic kidney disease	8	10.8%
Venous insufficiency	3	4.1%
Malignancy	2	2.7%

Supplementary Information

Supplementary Table 1. Patient medical history at registry enrollment.

PTID	Medical History
1	CHF s/p AICD, Hyperlipidemia, Recurrent GI bleeding from small bowel angioectasias, Iron deficiency anemia, Peripheral Vascular disease
2	Chronic insomnia, Major depressive disorder, POLYNEUROPATHY, UNSPECIFIED ATRIAL FIBRILLATION, Anemia, Hyperlipidemia, Hypertension, Diabetes mellitus Type 2
3	Cellulitis of left lower extremity, Pressure Ulcer-Left ankle, Stage 2, Hypertension, Left Breast Cyst, Osteoporosis, Systolic CHF
4	Hypertension, Peripheral Vascular disease, Diabetes mellitus Type 2
5	Diabetes mellitus Type 2, Acquired absence of other right toe(s), Type 2 diabetes mellitus with diabetic polyneuropathy, Essential hypertension
6	Peripheral Vascular disease, Diabetes mellitus Type 2
7	Local infection of the skin and subcutaneous tissue, unspecified, Other hereditary and idiopathic neuropathies
8	Peripheral Vascular disease, Type 2 diabetes mellitus with foot ulcer, Type 2 diabetes mellitus with diabetic polyneuropathy, Essential hypertension, Idiopathic Progressive Neuropathy, Local infection of the skin and subcutaneous tissue, unspecified
9	Venous insufficiency (chronic) (peripheral), Hypertension, Heart disease, Chronic venous hypertension (idiopathic) with ulcer of left lower extremity, Diabetes mellitus Type 2
10	Peripheral Vascular disease, Chronic Heart failure, End stage renal disease, Diabetes mellitus Type 2 , Diabetic Polyneuropathy
11	Diabetes mellitus Type 2, Diabetic polyneuropathy
12	Hallux valgus (acquired), left foot, Hallux valgus (acquired), right foot, Gout
13	Peripheral neuropathy, Hypertension
14	Not recorded
15	Not recorded
16	Renal Failure, Chronic Kidney Disease, High Cholesterol, Hypertension, Diabetes mellitus Type 2
17	Diabetes mellitus Type 2, High Cholesterol, Glaucoma, Chronic Kidney Disease, Lymphedema
18	Diabetes mellitus Type 2
19	Diabetes, High Cholesterol
20	Cholesterol High, Arthritis, Hypertension, Abdominal Hernia, Skin Ulcer
21	Not recorded
22	Peripheral Arterial Occlusive Disease
23	Diabetes Mellitus Type 2, High Cholesterol
24	Diabetes Mellitus Type 2
25	Diabetes Mellitus Type 2
26	Arthritis, Hypertension, Cholesterol
27	Arthritis, Diabetes, Pressure Ulcer, Osteoarthritis, Chronic Skin Ulcer, Artery of Lower Extremity
28	Diabetes Mellitus Type 2, HYPERTENSION
29	Diabetes mellitus Type 2
30	Diabetes mellitus Type 2
31	DVT, High Cholesterol, Hypertension, Diabetes mellitus Type 2
32	Diabetes mellitus Type 2, High Cholesterol
33	Diabetes mellitus Type 2, Hypertension
34	Diabetes mellitus Type 2, Diabetic peripheral neuropathy
35	Diabetes mellitus Type 2, Amputation- Left 5th Toe
36	Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus, Cellulitis of left lower limb, Corns and callosities), Non-prs chronic ulcer oth prt left foot w fat layer exposed
37	Foot drop, left foot, Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus with Diabetic Polyneuropathy, Hypertension, Type 2 diabetes mellitus with foot ulcer, Diabetes mellitus Type 2
38	Hypertension, Venous insufficiency, Atrial fibrillation, Congestive heart failure, Diabetes mellitus Type 2
39	Diabetes mellitus Type 2, Diabetes Mellitus Type 2 with Polyneuropathy, Charcot's Joint, Bilateral Ankle and Foot, Hypertension
40	Soft mass removal and skin flap closure of R foot, Anxiety, Depression, Ulcer of R plantar foot, Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus with Diabetic Polyneuropathy

41	Diabetes mellitus Type 2, Diabetic Neuropathy, Hypertension
42	DVT lower extremities, Chronic Venous Hypertension, Diabetes mellitus Type 2
43	Chronic venous insufficiency, Diabetes mellitus Type 2
44	Diabetes mellitus Type 2, Neuropathy
45	Not recorded
46	History of kidney cancer, Cancer of the skin, basal cell, Factor 5 Leiden mutation, heterozygous, DVT, Hypothyroidism, Diabetes mellitus Type 2
47	Acute Kidney Injury, Cellulitis, Atrial fibrillation, Hypokalemia, Chronic Ulcer left leg
48	Diabetes mellitus Type 2, Hypertension
49	CAD (coronary artery disease), Diabetes mellitus Type 2, Hyperlipidemia, Hypertension
50	Pancreatitis, Hypertension, Testicular hypofunction, Hyperlipidemia, Diabetes mellitus Type 2
51	Dilated cardiomyopathy, Insulin Dependent Diabetes Mellitus, Chronic Kidney Disease

Supplementary Table 2. Patient wound-level summaries for all wounds.

PTID	Wound	Wound type	Duration, days	N visits	N applications	Products	Baseline area, cm ²	Final area, cm ²	Percent change	TTC, days
1	1	Other	6 months	3	3	PMDL	3.0	1.1	62.0	
2	1	DFU	3 years	10	10	PMDL/PMTL-B	83.0	63.9	23.0	
3	1	PU	1 month	9	1	PMTL-B	1.0	0.0	100.0	7
	2	PU	4 weeks	9	7	PMDL/PMTL-B	1.0	0.0	100.0	49
4	1	DFU	7 months	7	7	PMDL/PMTL-B	2.0	1.0	50.5	
	2	DFU	7 months	7	7	PMDL/PMTL-B	2.5	1.6	36.0	
	3	DFU	7 months	7	7	PMDL/PMTL-B	0.5	0.1	76.0	
	4	Other	2 months	7	1	PMDL	1.2	0.0	100.0	
	5	PU	7 months	7	7	PMDL/PMTL-B	3.4	2.1	37.5	
5	1	DFU	2 years	2	1	PMTL-B	81.0	82.8	-2.2	
6	1	VLU	1 year	8	7	PMDL/PMTL-B	1.0	0.0	100.0	56
7	1	Other	4 weeks	2	1	PMDL	1.0	0.0	100.0	7
8	1	PU	3 months	9	8	PMDL/PMTL-B	4.0	0.0	100.0	55
9	1	DFU	1 month	5	5	PMTL-A	9.0	1.9	78.7	
10	1	VLU	3 months	5	4	PMDL/PMTL-B	7.0	0.0	100.0	28
11	1	DFU	8 weeks	2	1	PMTL-B	1.0	0.0	100.0	6
12	1	Other	1 month	9	8	PMTL-B	2.0	0.0	100.0	63
13	1	VLU	2 months	2	2	PMTL-B	1.0	1.0	0.0	
14	1	DFU	4 weeks	4	4	PMDL	18.0	9.2	48.9	
15	1	DFU	4 weeks	4	4	PMDL	28.0	22.8	18.8	
16	1	PU	1 year	10	10	PMDL/PMTL-B	6.0	6.0	0.0	
17	1	DFU	8 months	8	8	PMDL/PMTL-B	4.0	6.3	-56.3	
	2	DFU	8 months	8	8	PMDL/PMTL-B	3.0	6.0	-100.0	
18	1	DFU	1 year	4	4	PMDL	5.0	0.5	90.0	
	2	DFU	1 year	4	2	PMDL/PMTL-B	1.6	4.0	-156.4	
19	1	DFU	1 year	10	10	PMTL-B	9.0	4.9	46.0	
20	1	DFU	1 month	4	3	PMTL-B	9.0	2.5	72.2	
	2	DFU	1 month	4	4	PMTL-B	12.0	8.0	33.3	
21	1	DFU	4 months	4	4	PMTL-B	2.0	0.5	73.0	
22	1	DFU	5 months	2	2	PMTL-B	3.0	1.4	52.9	
23	1	DFU	11 months	10	10	PMDL/PMTL-B	11.0	14.0	-27.3	
24	1	DFU	2 months	10	10	PMDL/PMTL-B	30.4	1.6	94.9	
25	1	DFU	2 months	4	4	PMDL/PMTL-B	2.6	0.8	68.8	
26	1	DFU	3 months	8	8	PMDL/PMTL-B	9.0	4.4	51.0	
	2	DFU	3 months	8	8	PMDL/PMTL-B	3.0	1.2	59.7	
	3	DFU	3 months	8	8	PMDL/PMTL-B	42.0	35.5	15.5	
27	1	DFU	10 months	7	5	PMDL/PMTL-B	1.0	0.0	100.0	35
	2	DFU	10 months	7	7	PMDL/PMTL-B	6.0	1.3	78.0	
	3	DFU	10 months	7	7	PMDL/PMTL-B	46.0	22.1	52.1	
28	1	DFU	3 months	8	8	PMDL/PMTL-B	3.0	0.5	85.0	
29	1	DFU	1 year	3	3	PMDL/PMTL-B	76.8	77.8	-1.3	
30	1	DFU	5 months	5	5	PMDL/PMTL-B	5.5	1.0	82.0	
31	1	DFU	7 months	6	6	PMDL/PMTL-B	2.0	0.3	87.5	
	2	DFU	7 months	6	3	PMDL/PMTL-B	2.4	0.0	100.0	21
32	1	DFU	5 months	6	6	PMDL/PMTL-B	14.3	2.4	83.0	
33	1	DFU	1 month	2	2	PMTL-B	2.9	1.3	55.9	
34	1	DFU	2 months	2	2	PMTL-B	4.2	4.2	0.0	
35	1	DFU	7 weeks	9	6	PMTL-B	14.0	0.8	94.3	
36	1	DFU	8 weeks	7	7	PMTL-B	1.0	0.0	96.0	
37	1	DFU	3 months	7	7	PMTL-B	1.0	0.1	90.0	
38	1	DFU	1 month	7	7	PMTL-B	12.0	14.2	-18.4	
39	1	DFU	11 months	5	5	PMTL-B	3.8	2.3	40.0	

40	1	DFU	4 months	1	1	PMTL-B	0.3	0.3	0.0	
41	1	DFU	3 years	3	3	PMTL-B	31.2	25.5	18.3	
42	1	VLU	1 year	6	6	PMTL-B	4.0	2.4	40.0	
43	1	DFU	1 year	6	6	PMTL-A	32.2	16.5	48.8	
44	1	DFU	2 months	10	9	PMTL-B	4.6	0.8	82.6	
45	1	PU	1 month	3	1	PMTL-B	0.2	0.0	100.0	14
	2	PU	2 months	3	3	PMTL-B	1.0	0.2	84.0	
46	1	DFU	Unknown	6	6	PMTL-A	12.0	0.0	100.0	49
	2	DFU	Unknown	6	5	PMTL-A	27.5	0.0	100.0	40
47	1	Other	2 months	2	2	PMTL-B	18.0	14.0	22.2	
48	1	DFU	4 years	6	6	PMTL-B	1.8	0.7	60.0	
49	1	DFU	6 weeks	3	3	PMTL-A	80.0	56.0	30.0	
50	1	DFU	5 months	3	3	PMTL-B	1.0	0.3	70.0	
51	1	DFU	1 month	3	2	PMTL-A	0.3	1.0	-300.0	
	2	DFU	1 month	3	3	PMTL-A	0.1	0.0	100.0	